

A PERSPECTIVE SHIFT FOR A HUMAN-LIFE-FRIENDLY PRODUCT SERVICE SYSTEM (PSS)

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ABSTRACT

Sustainability has become an important issue for both producers and consumers. On the production side, the Product Service System (PSS) has targeted environmental protection, economic value, and consumer satisfaction, while consumers have also sought to minimize environmental repercussions while maintaining efficiency. The ultimate goal of the PSS is to promote both sustainable production and sustainable consumption, in that sustainable production can only be achieved when the life cycle includes sustainable consumption. In other words, the PSS should maintain environmental value while improving consumers' lives, and should influence not only the moment of consumption but also consumers' lives as a whole.

Based on this insight, PSS developers seek to understand and reflect the context of usage and consumers' needs from the beginning. However, these attempts are often considered only in terms of product or service usage, rather than in terms of human daily life or a comprehensive consumer life pattern. Human daily life consists of various activities, and these activities are related to one another. Therefore, the development of a human-life-friendly PSS can be easier considering the suggested point of view in this paper.

Therefore, this study selects and structures activities closely related to product service usage, and analyzes 59 PSS cases based on 61 consumer life domains selected from the American Time Use Survey (ATUS) Activity Coding Lexicon to identify which life domains a PSS can satisfy. By examining the differences in PSS offerings for specific activities, this research provides the basic information for successful human-life-friendly PSS development in the future.

KEYWORDS: *Product Service System, Human-life-friendly PSS, Sustainable consumption, Consumer life structure, Time use survey,*

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has become an important issue for both production and consumption sides. On the production side, the Product Service System (PSS) has targeted environmental protection, economic value, and consumer satisfaction, while the consumption side has also sought to minimize environmental repercussions while maintaining efficiency. The PSS ultimate goal is to promote both sustainable production and consumption, in that sustainable production can only be achieved by sustainable consumption in terms of the life cycle. In other words, the PSS should be able to maintain environmental value while improving consumers' lives, and should influence not only the moment of consumption, but also the consumer's daily life as a whole.

Based on this insight, PSS developers seek to understand and reflect on the context of usage and the needs of consumers

from the beginning. However, these attempts are being considered only in terms of product or service usage, and not in terms of the daily life of a comprehensive consumer's life pattern. Human daily life consists of various activities, and these activities are related to one another. Therefore, the development of a human-life-friendly PSS should be easier if PSS developers consider how a consumer's life is composed, what kind of activities s/he is involved in, and how they are related to each other, as well as what elements of an individual's life can be improved upon.

Therefore, this study selects and structures the activities closely related to the usage of product service, and analyzes existing PSS cases based on the consumer life domain in order to identify the life domains that a PSS can or cannot satisfy. Also, by discovering the links between specific activities, this research suggests a possible consumer life domain for future successful human life-friendly PSS development. The research

will be conducted as follows: First, how a consumer's daily life is composed and how the components are linked will be examined. Time use surveys may be a useful tool for this. A time use survey is a survey that collects a country's detailed individual 24-hour activity records via record/interview methods for various purposes, and it is conducted at a nation-wide level in places like the US, Japan, Korea, and European countries. Methods and survey population size may vary in different countries. Data is collected by recording participants' activity over a 24-hour period into a diary with his/her demographic characteristics. The participants are required to record how, where, and with whom they spend their day in the diary.

Recorded content also includes non-market activities such as childcare and volunteer work. The Activity Lexicon, which will be used in this study, may be a useful reference to understand all of the activity elements that make up a subject's life. In order to structuralize consumers' daily lives, this research will use the 2012 American Time Use Survey (ATUS) Activity Coding Lexicon, which best categorizes activity elements in detail. The ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon is a three-tiered classification system with seventeen first-tier categories. Each of the first-tier categories has two additional levels of detail. Among these, activity elements that can be achieved using a product or service will be selected. Then, this research investigates which activity elements in a life structure are satisfied by 59 different business cases that employ the PSS concept. Each PSS case will then be categorized as product-oriented, use-oriented, or result-oriented, based on the providing-method classification suggested in Mont (2002) and Tukker (2004), and placed into a satisfying activity element.

If a case satisfies multiple activity elements, the case will be selected for all satisfied activity elements. After being analyzed, the results will be used to identify which activity is satisfied (or not satisfied) by PSS, and its main providing-method in terms of consumer life. Also, this paper will identify linkages between activities (whether one activity is linked with another simultaneously or chronologically) through time use survey panel data analysis, thus suggesting additional activities or challenging PSS providing-method on top of existing PSS activities. Moreover, using the linkage between activities, this paper will provide basic data for the development of new PSS ideas.

BACKGROUND

Sustainable consumption

While sustainable consumption has been officially emphasized since the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (the Rio Conference) in 1992, the individual ethics aspect of this subject has been studied from as early as the 1970s. Existing studies deal with the actions and motivations of consumers who consider the environment during the purchase, consumption, and disposal of a product (Anderson &

Cunningham, 1972; Henion, 1972; Webster, 1975). However, these studies focus on the motivation of a particular eco-friendly consumer group, thus emphasizing socioeconomic responsibility based on individual consumer's awareness.

More lively debate on sustainability in the consumer domain began to emerge in 1997 after the 1992 Rio Conference. Early studies were limited to improvements in the manufacturing process and reducing industrial waste; the focus has since shifted to the life cycle perspective, including both manufacturing and consumption, thus expanding the scope from the supply domain to include the consumer domain.

Sustainable development is thus recognized as requiring a dematerialized consumption pattern that can decrease resource and energy usage while considering the environmental repercussions of a product and its manufacturing process, and satisfying consumer needs. In light of this trend, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) established its sustainable consumption program in 1998; many consumption-aspect studies have been conducted since (UNEP, 2002).

The early studies on sustainable consumption were mainly informational; governmental organizations conducted policy research and various NGOs created ethical guidelines to minimize consumption levels. Hansen and Schrader (1997), and Heiskanen and Pantzar (1997), developed a consumer behavior model of sustainable consumption. Moreover, studies have been conducted to determine the environmental affects of various consumption scenarios (Jager, 2000), to analyze resource- and energy-intensive consumption patterns, and to provide suggestions to address extreme consumption (Brown & Cameron, 2000; Röpke, 1999, 2001). However, while these attempts may have changed the public's perception of the subject matter, they failed to actualize a change in actual behavior patterns (Moisander, 2001). Most of these studies were limited to policy-level research (Mont, 2004).

During the mid-2000s, several scholars began to discuss ideas related to sharing-based collaborative consumption, founded on the spread of the Internet; hence, researchers started to focus on inducing changes in societal behavior. Collaborative consumption was initially defined as individual consumption of wealth or a service shared between individuals or multiple persons (Felson & Spaeth, 1978). This pattern of consumption activity must be dealt with in terms of both activities involving two individuals, and activities involving an individual and a society (Hawley, 1950); therefore, in order to understand collaborative consumption, both the consuming body and the specific context of the consumption activity, including location and precedents, must be considered (Felson & Spaeth, 1978).

These concepts of collaborative consumption, however, are limited to consumption behavior, and do not include the effectiveness of and satisfaction with such consumption behavior. Collaborative consumption has been out of discussion since the 2000s, when the rapid spread of the Internet led the term to be integrated with the notion of sharing. Belk (2007) defines sharing as an event in which more than two owners of the

same material benefit from cost-effectiveness, thus enhancing the consumption value. He suggested the idea of sharing as an alternative to private ownership, adding that effectiveness and satisfaction can be improved by sharing not only materials but also knowledge, liability, authority, voluntary leases, and resource allocation.

Lessig (2008) first introduced the term ‘sharing economy’, and proposed an economic system based on societal relations between communities — rather than on money — and increases the value of intangible/tangible wealth through sharing, exchange, lease, and utilization. However, Lessig’s (2008) work is limited to a theoretical suggestion.

The existing studies on sustainable consumption have involved conceptual discussion at the behavioral policy level, focusing on individual consumers or a specific moment of consumption; moreover, the preceding research is limited to alternatives in the consumption domain, and lacks a comprehensive life cycle perspective including manufacturing aspects. In order to promote realistic sustainable consumption, an eco-friendly product or service must not be limited to a specific moment of usage, but be expanded to be involved in overall daily life. Therefore, fundamental research reflecting consumers’ daily lives, and what type of life needs need to be satisfied, must be conducted. This information will allow developers to better understand consumers’ lives in terms of the consumption domain and can be incorporated at the development stage of a product/service.

Product Service System

The Product Service System (PSS), first introduced by Goedkoop (1999), is defined as a system that satisfies a customer’s needs and includes a product/service, and the relevant network and infrastructure developed to minimize environmental repercussions relative to the existing business model. Goedkoop proposed the PSS as an alternative to promote value by linking products and services, thus actualizing economic value and minimizing environmental damage simultaneously.

Mont (2002) collected various studies related to the PSS concept and put them together under the PSS system. Mont pointed out that existing studies involved only a single element — such as product usage, leasing, maintenance, and service — and that when all elements were integrated into one system with the product-service life cycle perspective, both environmental concerns and the interests of the interested parties could be addressed. Manzini (2003) also argued that environmental value could be promoted via the optimization of resource usage between interested parties using the product-service life cycle perspective.

The definition of the PSS may differ from scholar to scholar: It may be defined as a pre-designed system of products, supporting infrastructure and necessary networks that fulfil a user’s needs on the market, have a smaller environmental impact than separate product and services with the same function fulfilment and are self-learning (Centre for Sustainable Design, 2001). A PSS may also be defined as consisting

of tangible products and intangible services, designed and combined so that they are jointly capable of fulfilling specific customer needs (Brandsotter, 2003), or as a solution offered for sale that involves both a product and a service element, to deliver the required functionality (Wong, 2004). All of these definitions share the same core aspect of sustainability. Therefore, in this study, we define the PSS as ‘a system or a business model with ultimate sustainability that, via product and service integration, satisfies consumer needs from both the product and the service perspectives while decreasing environmental damage’.

In the early stages of PSS conceptualization, research of PSS components and their types was actively conducted. Goedkoop (1999) attempted to categorize the PSS according to the product service ratio. The research divides the PSS into four categories based on the type of linkage between the product and the service for functional satisfaction. The first category is the service-attached product (Ps), in which service is based on the product’s life cycle — such as car maintenance service, or after-sales service of a refrigerator. The second category is the product-attached service (Sp), in which a product is delivered in the form of a service — such as an ATM service. The third category is a form of product service system development, and the last category is a type that replaces the entire existing PSS. The proportions of the four categories may vary because of technological and environmental changes.

Mont (2002) attempted a sporadic approach to the existing PSS. Mont pointed out the lack of a unifying understanding of the components comprising the PSS, and suggested the following concepts: (1) the PSS is composed of a product, a service, or a combination of both product and service; (2) a service may occur at the time of sales, such as assistance purchasing a product or the explanation of a product manual; (3) the product usage concept is divided into utility from direct usage and utility from the provider; (4) maintenance and customer support are based on the product’s life cycle; and (5) the PSS includes the disposal stage of a product — recycling, collection, reuse, and so on.

Figure 1. Main and subcategories of PSS (Tukker, 2004)

Tischner et al. (2002) conducted research on the relationship between the PSS and the traditional concept of products and services. The traditional concepts of products and services were placed at the ends of a spectrum, and the PSS was categorized into a product-oriented PSS, a use-oriented PSS, and a result-oriented PSS, according to the position on the spectrum. In a product-oriented PSS, a user or customer owns a product with a renewable service contract or a maintenance and upgrade customer support service. In a use-oriented PSS, a provider owns a product, and usage of the product is shared among customers through various methods. The provider owns the product but has the responsibility to make the product available for usage in return for a certain fee. In a result-oriented PSS, a customer and a provider agree on the required result of the service; however, there is no set product. In this way, the provider can use the minimum amount of human and physical resource to deliver the result agreed upon beforehand.

Tukker (2004) attempts to subdivide the aforementioned three types of PSS, suggesting that the previous study failed to clarify the different environmental and economic characteristics of each type. According to Tukker, the product-oriented PSS is subdivided into (1) product-related service and (2) consultation and advice; the use-oriented PSS is divided into (3) product leases, (4) product lease sharing, and (5) product usage sharing; and the result-oriented PSS is divided into (6) management and outsourcing, (7) service fee per unit, and (8) functional result.

Time use survey

A time use survey is a multi-purpose survey that collects comprehensive data on how a domestic population spends its time. These types of surveys are conducted nationally in various countries including the United States, Japan, Korea, and European countries; however, the survey period, method, and timetable categories differ in different countries. The timetable categories used in this study are subdivided into three based on the location, purpose, and situation of various consumer activities. The first known survey on the use of time is Bevans' research on male workers' use of time in 1913. At the governmental or research institution level, relevant surveys have been conducted since the 1920s in the United States (Cornell University), Russia, and the United Kingdom (British Broadcasting Corporation). In the 1950s, America's CBC used a diary in its survey and report, providing a framework for modern-day time usage surveys. In the United States, time use surveys were conducted on a small scale by individual institutions until 1991, when the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics developed the national American Time Use Survey (ATUS) in four stages; an annual survey has been conducted since 2003.

The Japan Broadcasting Corporation (NHK) conducted the first time use survey in Japan in 1969, and since 1976, the Statistics Bureau of Japan has conducted a large-scale survey every five years. In Korea, the Rural Development Administration began conducting a time use survey in 1979 to analyze farming households' life patterns. From 1981 to 1995, the Korean

Broadcasting System conducted the National Time Use Survey, and Statistics Korea has been conducting a national time use survey every five years since 1999. An international time use survey was first conducted in the mid-1960s, and Eurostat has conducted these surveys periodically since the 1990s.

RESEARCH METHOD

Structure of consumers' daily life

Before identifying the consumer life domain satisfied by a PSS, this study categorizes the different activities within the consumption life domain. For the time use categorization in this research, we refer to the 2012 ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon, which has the most detailed activity elements. The ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon is a three-tiered classification system with seventeen first-tier categories. Each of the first-tier categories has two additional levels of detail (Bureau of Labor Statistics & U.S. Census Bureau, 2013). We shortened the list of approximately 480 activity elements to 61 activity elements based on the following criteria: (1) the activity element can be satisfied using a product or service, and (2) an individual can autonomously select or utilize a product or service for the activity element. The resulting 61 activity elements are shown in Table 1.

NO.	ACTIVITIES
1	Activities rel. to purchasing/selling/renting real estate
2	Appliance, tool, and toy set-up, rent, repair, & maintenance
3	Arts and crafts as a hobby
4	Attending meetings for personal interest (not volunteering)
5	Attending or hosting parties/receptions/ceremonies
6	Attending, watching sporting/recreational Events
7	Banking
8	Building and repairing furniture
9	Care for animals and pets (not veterinary care)
10	Civic obligations & participation
11	Collecting as a hobby
12	Comparison shopping
13	Computer use for leisure (exc. games)
14	Eating and drinking
15	Exterior cleaning
16	Exterior repair, improvements, & decoration
17	Financial management
18	Food and drink preparation
19	Food presentation
20	Grocery shopping
21	Health-related self-care
22	Heating and cooling(building)
23	HH & personal e-mail and messages
24	HH & personal mail & messages (except e-mail)
25	Hobbies, except arts & crafts and collecting
26	Home security
27	Household & personal organization and planning
28	Interior arrangement, decoration, & repairs
29	Interior cleaning
30	Kitchen and food clean-up
31	Laundry

NO.	ACTIVITIES
32	Lawn, garden, and houseplant care
33	Listening to the radio
34	Listening to/playing music (not radio)
35	Obtaining licenses & paying fines, fees, taxes
36	Participating in sports, exercise, or recreation
37	Personal emergencies
38	Personal/private activities
39	Playing games
40	Ponds, pools, and hot tubs care
41	Purchasing food (not groceries)
42	Purchasing gas(energy)
43	Reading for personal interest
44	Relaxing and Leisure
45	Security procedures rel. to consumer purchases
46	Security procedures rel. to govt svcs/civic obligations
47	Security procedures rel. to professional/personal svcs.
48	Sewing, repairing, & maintaining textiles
49	Shopping, except groceries, food and gas
50	Sleeping
51	Socializing and communicating with others
52	Storing interior hh items, inc. food
53	Telephone calls (to or from)
54	Television and movies (not religious)
55	Tobacco and drug use
56	Traveling/mobility/car
57	Vehicle repair and maintenance
58	Walking / exercising / playing with animals
59	Washing, dressing and grooming oneself
60	Waiting for the activity(including reservation)
61	Writing for personal interest

Table 1. 61 Activities from ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon

Data collection

For this research, we collected 59 actual PSS cases from Korea, the United States, and Europe. Each PSS case includes a product-service business model; pure services and pure products are excluded and only business to consumer (B2C)

services and products are included. Moreover, cases should be well known by consumers' in each case oriented country and the business should be running still now. The cases are selected from PSS researches such as UNEP article and companies' web sites.

Analysis process

In this section, we identify which activity element each of the collected 59 PSS cases satisfies. Following the classifications provided by Mont (2002) and Tukker (2004), the PSS cases are divided into product-oriented, use-oriented, and result-oriented categories, and each case is assigned to a relevant activity element. If one case satisfies multiple activity elements, it is placed under multiple activity elements. The result is then analyzed to identify activities that are (not) satisfied by the existing PSS, and their main method of supply, in order to discover the life domains on which the PSS should focus in the future. Table 2 illustrates the framework used in the analysis.

RESULT

Figure 2 shows a summary of the results. From the analysis, it can be identified that many PSS development attempts have been made for most of the activities within consumers' life structure. This is because, in many cases, PSS development takes place as a form of adding peripheral activities to core activities based on the life cycle perspective. The result also shows that each PSS is involved in an average of 2.6 different activities; this illustrates that the current PSS is focused on a specific activity rather than overall life as a total service. Sports and leisure activities represent the most varied forms of PSS cases; however, there were few PSS cases related to public service, telephone calls, storage, entertainment, private activities, medical activities, janitorial services, and home management. This is because the pure service model better satisfies the aforementioned activities than does the PSS.

ACT.	PSS CASE	AIR	AMAZON	NIKE +	ZIPCAR	WOOGJIN	I TUNES	DELL	ADIDAS	TOTAL
		BNB	KINDLE	IPOD		CDI		RUNNING	SHOP	
		P001	P002	P003	P004	P056	P057	P058	P059	
	CASE NO.	USE	PRODUCT	PRODUCT	USE	PRODUCT	PRODUCT	PRODUCT	USE	
1	Activities rel. to purchasing/selling/renting real estate									0
2	Appliance, tool, and toy set-up, rent, repair, & maintenance (by self)									0
3	Arts and crafts as a hobby									0
4	Attending meeting for personal interest (not volunteering)									0
5	Attending or hosting parties/receptions/ceremonies									0
6	Attending, watching sporting/recreational Events			1						1
7	Banking									0
56	Traveling/mobility/car				1				1	1
57	Vehicle repair and maintenance				1				1	1
58	Walking/exercising/playing with animals			1						1
59	Washing, dressing and grooming oneself						1			1
60	Waiting for the activity (including reservation)									0
61	Writing for personal interest					1				1
	Total	0	0	2	2	1	1	0	2	-
	Average of Activities per each PSS Case									-

Table 2. Example Sheet of Analysis Process

Figure 2. Result of PSS Case Analysis Based on Consumer Activity Element

The product-oriented PSS type is most common, accounting for 29 cases; there are 17 use-oriented cases, and a relatively low 13 result-oriented cases. This shows that the PSS still develops in a product-oriented way, and that increases in material flow are still the main focus. For transportation-related activities such as vehicle or bicycle use, the use-oriented type of PSS is most common, and for purchasing activities like shopping, the product-oriented type of PSS is most common because of the inherent nature of the activity. It is not definitive which type of PSS is most efficient for a specific activity; however, an attempt to develop different types to satisfy the same activity may be useful.

In the case of energy-purchasing activities, the car rental activity and the energy-purchasing activity are combined as a use-oriented PSS. This illustrates that it is possible to provide different types of PSS by integrating different activities. The result also showed that the use-oriented PSS type is less accessible for social and communication activities. Social activity must be consolidated when planning a use-oriented PSS.

CONCLUSION

This study analyses some current PSS cases from the consumer life perspective and provides evidence to help in the pursuit of human life — friendly PSS developments. In order to do so, we structuralize consumers' daily lives using the ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon and analyze which life domains are satisfied by current PSS cases based on PSS supply type (product/use/result oriented). The result shows that various existing PSS cases satisfy consumers throughout their overall structuralized life domains. Each PSS case satisfies an average of 2.6 activity elements. This shows that as developers attempt to develop PSS types for various activities, a single PSS cannot act as a total service that satisfies many aspects of consumer daily life. Moreover, each PSS case tends to satisfy one main activity and several additional activities. In other words, integrating different consumer daily activities can be the main source of new ideas for PSS development. Moreover, the result shows that only one type of PSS is currently provided for certain activities, which opens up the possibility to develop different types of PSS to improve these activities.

Current PSS tends to focus on the consumer's needs and user context, which is directly related to the steps on the specific user process. From this point of view, the PSS can meet what people want, but may not really improve their quality of life. Better understanding of the consumers' life structure at the beginning of PSS design stage can be helpful to make the PSS more fitting for human life and closer to sustainability.

But this paper only refers ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon for the analysis, not the actual data of ATUS, so results of the study may suggest limited implication about the consumers' real life structure. In future research, identifying the relationship between specific activities that can be integrated with one another based on ATUS data, and additional analysis of further PSS cases, may facilitate more concrete and empirical proposals.

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